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Evaluating the potential of persistent luminescence in counteracting urban overheating

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Abstract. In recent years, the use of numerical simulations to model real atmospheric conditions over cities has become increasingly popular. One of the primary objectives of these models is to assess the efficacy of various strategies for mitigating the Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon. At the same time, researchers have developed and studied new adaptive materials for building applications that aim to reduce buildings' energy consumption and improve urban microclimate conditions, while performing radiative cooling. Among the new generation of passive cooling solutions, persistent luminescent (PL) materials have emerged as a cutting-edge option for energy-saving purposes, owing to their ability to reject the incident solar radiation through both reflection and light emission. Here, the Princeton Urban Canopy Model (PUCM) is used to evaluate the potential of an advanced PL roof coating to counteract urban overheating. The phenomenon of persistent luminescence is modeled for the first time, taking advantage of experimentally obtained parameters coming from previous studies. Results demonstrate how persistent luminescence can effectively mitigate surface overheating reducing the roof's surface temperature and net shortwave radiation up to 1.15 °C and 35 W/m² respectively, with consequent benefits to the overall energy balance of the envelope. Such results may be further increased with the optimization of PL materials for engineering solutions.

1. Introduction

The Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon refers to the fact that cities are hotter than nearby rural areas, and it is caused by factors such as the use of artificial materials that retain heat and have low cooling capacity [1]. With urban expansion and population growth, UHI has become a threat to the livability of cities and poses risks to human health, especially for vulnerable populations [2]. UHI also has implications for building energy consumption, leading to increased cooling loads and energy costs. To address UHI, sustainable urban planning and design are crucial, including the use of green infrastructure and cool materials [3]. Sohaili et al. [4] have shown that green roofs can reduce surface temperatures by 4.3 °C compared to traditional dark roofs. Additionally, green roofs can lead to a 3.7 °C reduction in average air temperature and an 8.46% reduction in relative humidity compared to standard bitumen roofs [5]. Despite the promising results, implementing such applications requires extensive economic and practical efforts. For this reason, the attention of the scientific community has focused also on the development of innovative roof applications, characterized by optimized solar reflectance and thermal

emittance capability, i.e., cool roof solutions [6]. As a matter of fact, surface treatments are not only cost-effective, but also easy to implement. Moreover, they require significantly less maintenance than traditional green roofs, while still providing comparable temperature reductions to vegetated roofs. Roof paintings have been extensively studied by Synnefa et al. [7]. They found that certain coatings made of transparent polymers and white pigments can significantly reduce surface temperature during the day and night under summer conditions. Levinson et al. [8] found that using NIR-reflective roof tile coatings can result in a reduction in surface temperature and heat flux. More recently, thermochromic materials, which change their optical properties based on temperature, have been investigated to reduce winter heat loss [9]. Fabiani et al. [10] demonstrated that an innovative thermochromic roof configuration can reduce cooling load by 6.59% per square meter, slightly less than a more common cool application, but with no negative effects in winter.

Among the latest generation of cool materials for the built environment, photoluminescent solutions have emerged owing to their ability to combine light reflection and emission [11]. Despite the numerous studies suggesting the suitability of photoluminescence for several UHI mitigation solutions, most of the research available in literature is limited to laboratory-scale investigations focused on chemical compounds [12]. In the present study, the Princeton Urban Canopy Model (PUCM) has been employed to explore the potential application of photoluminescent roof coating as a UHI mitigation strategy. The study aims to investigate the advantages of optimized photoluminescent paintings over purely cool roofs at the inter-building scale. The numerical analyses have been critically evaluated to assess the expected benefits of introducing photoluminescence in the built environment.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Various commercially available pigments were selected in the frame of an innovative research and development project and considered as starting-point materials in this work. These pigments are typically dispersed into different solutions to create more complex prototypes that glow in the dark, such as glasses, ceramics, and coatings. The aim of encompassing different photoluminescent emission colors, spanning the entire visible spectrum, led to the selection of the seven compounds showed in figure 1. Table 1 provides a summary of the pigments' composition, including their hosting matrix and doping ions responsible for the specific color of emission, as already characterized in a previous research work [13]. Additionally, the quantum yield (QY), i.e., the ratio between the emitted over the absorbed photons, and the lifetime decay constant (τ) were taken into consideration. The latter was derived from the fitting curve describing the luminance decay of the photoluminescent emission over time ($L_v(t)$, equation 1) after the exposure to solar radiation has ended.

$$L_v(t) = L_v(t_0) \cdot e^{-\frac{1}{\tau}t} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Investigated photoluminescent pigments.

Table 1. Photoluminescent compounds and their main properties, i.e., the wavelength corresponding to the peak quantum yield (QY) and lifetime decay constant (T).

Code	Emission color	Matrix	Doping ions	$\lambda_{PL}[\text{nm}]$	$\lambda_{AE}[\text{nm}]$	QY	T
Y	Yellow	SrAl_2O_4	$\text{Eu}^{+2}, \text{Dy}^{+3}$	520	390	0.44	0.7792
B	Blue	$\text{Sr}_4\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{25}$	$\text{Eu}^{+2}, \text{Dy}^{+3}, \text{B}^{+3}$	490	370	0.88	1.2263
BS	Blue sky	$\text{Sr}_2\text{MgSi}_2\text{O}_7$	Eu, Dy	645	465	0.29	0.9138
P	Purple	CaAl_2O_4	$\text{Eu}^{+2}, \text{Nd}^{+3}, \text{La}^{+3}$	440	326	0.34	0.8607

R	Red	CaS	Eu	468	360	0.62	0.6269
O	Orange	Y ₂ O ₂ S	Eu	468, 626*	310	0.18	0.6350
W	White	YSr ₂ Al ₇ O ₁₄	Eu, Dy, B	445, 626*	330	0.30	0.7794

* The first wavelength corresponds to the first peak in the fluorescence profile, while the second corresponds to the maximum intensity of the emission.

2.2. Methodology

This study explores the potential of photoluminescent roof coating as a novel strategy for mitigating urban heat island (UHI) effects. To achieve this, we utilized the urban canopy model (PUCM) developed by Wang et al. [14] at Princeton University. The PUCM represents a single-layer urban canyon and incorporates a detailed surface exchange scheme that considers energy transport and hydrological processes over natural and/or engineering surfaces. The PUCM was validated for different climate conditions through in-field monitoring campaigns performed in different towns, in a stand-alone mode driven by 5 to 30-minute averaged meteorological data. In the model, the one-dimensional *interfacial energy balance* for an infinitesimally thin layer of each considered roof, wall, or ground surface, at the surface-air boundary, is defined as:

$$R_{net} = H + LE + G \quad (2)$$

where R_{net} is the net radiation, i.e., the sum of all net shortwave and longwave components, H is the convective sensible heat flux, LE is the latent heat flux, and G is the heat conducted into the wall, ground, or roof. The PUCM treats the canyon air as a separate thermal mass and any anthropogenic emissions are directly released into that mass (except for emissions due to space heating, which are indirectly represented by maintaining a fixed indoor temperature in the winter). Additionally, the model allows for detailed simulation of the thermo-optical properties of surfaces in a canyon environment, thanks to the ability of dividing surfaces into subfacets and accounting for the effects of trees. The model setup, including the specific properties of ground surfaces, building walls, and roofs is similar to those used by Ryu et al. [15] and enable the simulation of the effects of trees on the canyon environment. Table 2 summarizes the main properties of the materials involved in the model.

Table 2. Input parameters used in the PUCM for materials' properties.

Thermo-optic parameters	Value	Thermo-optic parameters	Value
Roof albedo (cool / dark)	0.66/0.16	Roof conductivity	0.94 W/(mK)
Wall albedo	0.25	Wall conductivity	0.94 W/(mK)
Ground albedo (asphalt/concrete)	0.10/0.20	Ground conductivity (asphalt/concrete)	1.20/2.00 W/(mK)
Roof emissivity	0.95	Roof heat capacity	1.40 MJ/(m ³ K)
Wall emissivity	0.95	Wall heat capacity	1.40 MJ/(m ³ K)
Ground emissivity (asphalt/concrete)	0.95/0.93	Ground heat capacity (asphalt/concrete)	1.80/1.30 MJ/(m ³ K)

2.2.1. Mathematical description of photoluminescence. A traditional building envelope surface of finite depth absorbs a net flux of shortwave and longwave radiation ($R_{SW,net} + R_{LW,net} = R_{net}$), and releases the resulting energy into the air as H and LE , and into the solid surface as G at the inner boundary of the surface. The finite depth also allows some storage of energy in the layer. For photoluminescent surfaces, an additional contribution to the rejection of the incident shortwave radiation must be introduced, which is a different energy dissipation term (Q_{PL}) due to radiation emission. Therefore, the surface energy balance of equation 1, with a photoluminescent layer and storage capacity, should be modified to the following equation:

$$R_{SW,net} + R_{LW,net} - LE - H - G - Q_{PL} = mc \frac{dT_{surf}}{dt} \quad (3)$$

where $mc \frac{dT_{surf}}{dt}$ is the amount of heat stored by the surface in time per unit area (it can be considered equal to zero for an infinitesimally thin layer to recover a form similar to equation 1). $R_{SW,net}$ is directly proportional to the incoming shortwave radiation (I_{SW}) and the shortwave solar absorbance (a). On the

other hand, $R_{LW,net}$ is related to the incoming longwave from the atmosphere (given as observed input to PUCM) and the outgoing longwave, which depends on the longwave surface reflectivity, the thermal emissivity (ϵ), the Stefan-Boltzmann constant (σ) and the fourth power of surface temperature (T_{surf}^4). Since the photoluminescent emission of the pigments investigated in this study occurs in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum (380-780 nm), representing the effect in PUCM simply requires the modification of the equation of the net shortwave radiation ($R_{SW,net}$) of a light-emitting surface to the following:

$$R_{SW,net} = I_{SW}(1 - \alpha) - Q_{PL} \quad (4)$$

where α is the albedo of the surface, determined by the material's capability of reflecting the incident solar radiation.

In recent years, Garshasbi et al. [13] proposed an analytical model to investigate the effect of fluorescent and optical properties on the cooling potential of photoluminescent materials. According to their work, Q_{PL} can be calculated as:

$$Q_{PL} = \frac{h \cdot c}{\lambda_{PL}} \int_{300nm}^{\lambda_{AE}} QY(\lambda) \frac{a(\lambda) \cdot I_{SW} \cdot \varphi(\lambda)}{\frac{h \cdot c}{\lambda}} d\lambda = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{PL}} \int_{300nm}^{\lambda_{AE}} QY(\lambda) \cdot a(\lambda) \cdot \varphi(\lambda) \cdot \lambda \cdot d\lambda \right) \cdot I_{SW} \quad (5)$$

where h is the Planck constant; c is the speed of light; λ_{PL} and λ_{AE} correspond to the material's peak of emission and absorption respectively; $a(\lambda)$ is the material's solar absorption coefficient; I_{SW} is the incoming shortwave radiation; $\varphi(\lambda)$ is the spectral distribution of the global solar radiation according to the standard spectrum AM 1.5g. However, equation 5 does not give any information about the decay of the photoluminescent emission when the incoming energizing radiation is turned off; i.e., it describes a purely fluorescent material that is receiving radiation. For this reason, in this work, a model for the description of phosphorescence is introduced for the first time, moving from the equation of Grashasbi et al.:

$$Q_{PL} = \Psi(\lambda_{PL}, \lambda_{AE}, QY, a) \cdot I_{SW} - \tau \frac{dQ_{PL}}{dt} \quad (6)$$

where Ψ is a hypothetical dimensionless term including all the fluorescent properties (a , QY , λ_{PL} and λ_{AE}) and τ is the lifetime decay constant of the photoluminescent compound. Once the last term of the equation is discretized in time using a forward Euler method in PUCM or an equivalent model, the last equation is written as:

$$Q_{PL}^t = \frac{\Psi(\lambda_{PL}, \lambda_{AE}, QY, a)}{1 + \frac{\tau}{\Delta t}} \cdot I_{SW} + \frac{\tau}{1 + \frac{\tau}{\Delta t}} \frac{Q_{PL}^{t-\Delta t}}{\Delta t} \quad (7)$$

where $Q_{PL}^{t=0} = \Psi(\lambda_{PL}, \lambda_{AE}, QY, a)$ and Δt is a 10-second time step.

2.2.2. Numerical experiments design. Three different analyses were carried out in this work. The first analysis involved assessing the impact of photoluminescent roof coatings with different afterglow colors and benchmarking them against a traditional dark ($\alpha = 0.16$) and cool ($\alpha = 0.66$) non-luminescent roof. Simulations were performed for three sunny days (3-5 July 2011), to identify the most promising option for passive cooling purposes. The input parameters for the photoluminescence equation were obtained from in-lab experimental data presented in Table 1. The second analysis involved a deeper investigation of the best performing photoluminescent coating through monthly-averaged simulations during the hottest (July-August 2011) and the coldest months of the year (January-February 2012). This analysis aimed to assess the coating's impact on the overall energy balance of the roof. Finally, an ideal photoluminescent material with optimized properties (QY , a , and τ) was simulated to quantify the maximal potential of the coating for UHI mitigation. More in details, QY and a were considered in the maximum value they could achieve, i.e., 100% and 1 respectively. The simulations were driven by in-situ observations collected in Princeton, NJ, from a dedicated weather station with a 30-minute sampling rate. The urban canyon considered in this study had an aspect ratio (building height to canyon width) of 0.80 and an impervious area fraction of 0.84. The area was thus densely urbanized, but its spatial extent

was limited, which minimized the impact of the urban surface fluxes on the atmospheric variables and made it suitable for offline UCM applications and testing. The observations are obtained from a dedicated weather station, with a 5-minute sampling rate [14]. The atmospheric variables required for the simulations included air temperature, specific humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, shortwave and longwave solar radiation, and precipitation data. All these variables were interpolated from the original weather file to fit the simulation time interval of 10s.

3. Results

3.1. Comparison between photoluminescent coatings with different afterglow color

Figures 2 and 3 show the differences in surface temperature (ΔT_{surf}) and net shortwave radiation ($\Delta R_{\text{SW,net}}$) of a typical dark roof and cool roof, both non-luminescent, relative to their identical counterparts with a photoluminescent coating applied on the outer skin. In particular, three sunny days were simulated (3-5 July 2011) to detect the maximum impact of photoluminescence in the best-case scenario, i.e., under favorable weather conditions, with a good level of solar radiation and no clouds.

Results show how the red-emitting pigments (R) had the greatest cooling potential, providing for a maximum surface temperature reduction of around 0.75 °C if applied to a dark roof ($\alpha = 0.16$), and around 1.15 °C in the case of a cool roof ($\alpha = 0.66$). The net shortwave radiation was also reduced by about 35 W/m² in both cases. Blue- (B) and yellow- (Y) emitting coating resulted in less than half the cooling benefit in both ΔT_{surf} and $\Delta R_{\text{SW,net}}$, even if they showed good potential for lighting purposes in other studies [16, 17]. Blue sky (BS), white (W) and purple (P) pigments followed in order, while orange (O) afterglow did not provide a significant change in surface temperature and net shortwave radiation if compared to a non-luminescent cool or dark roof. For this reason, the R-emitting coating was investigated deeper through the hottest (July-August) and coldest (January-February) months of the year.

3.2. Best-performing roof coating and its possible optimization

Figures 4 and 5 represent the contribution of the red-emitting coating, selected in section 3.1 as the best-performing for UHI mitigation purposes, in comparison to the behavior of the non-luminescent roof with the same thermo-optical cool properties. The monthly-averaged profiles refer to the hottest (July-August, figure 4) and the coldest (January-February, figure 5) period of the year. The roof surface temperature (T_{roof}) and the net shortwave radiation ($R_{\text{SW,net}}$) were taken as reference parameters to compare the performance of the non-luminescent and red-emitting roof.

The behavior of the cool roof was generally good in terms of UHI mitigation potential during the hottest months of the year, when the envelope was positively affected by reduced radiative absorption of incoming solar radiation. However, the presence of a photoluminescent coating on the outer layer of the roof further reduced heat gains, with peak reductions in net shortwave radiation of 27.94 W/m², and roof temperature of 0.77 °C. The impact of photoluminescence during the coldest months, instead, inevitably negated part of the winter-time benefits of the UHI phenomenon, but its magnitude was significantly lower than the summer impact (max $\Delta R_{\text{SW,net}} = 16.85$ W/m²), resulting in a surface temperature reduction of only 0.38 °C if compared to the non-luminescent scenario.

The capability of the red-emitting roof coating to dampen the heat gains during summer with negligible effects for the winter period, paved the way for the investigation on the maximum benefits that could be obtained by applying an optimized photoluminescent material with ideal fluorescent properties. Three scenarios were hypothesized, modeling a photoluminescent coating with the following characteristics: (i) $QY = 100\%$ and $a = 1$ ($R_{\text{opt}(QY,a)}$); (ii) $\tau_{\text{id}} = \tau \times 10^4$ ($R_{\text{opt}(\tau \times 10^4)}$); (iii) $QY = 100\%$, $a = 1$ and $\tau_{\text{id}} = \tau \times 10^4$ ($R_{\text{opt}(QY,a, \tau \times 10^4)}$). Scenario (i) maximizes the optical potential of the material, while scenario (ii) extends its storage capacity and its re-emission time scale τ . Specifically, the effect on the net shortwave radiation and surface temperature reduction due to the optimized red-emitting coating were quantified and compared to the performance of a non-luminescent roof, during three sunny summer days (3-5 July 2011).

Figure 2. Differences in (a) superficial temperature (ΔT_{surf}) and (c) net SW radiation ($\Delta R_{SW,net}$) of the dark roof in its photoluminescent configuration and its non-luminescent version, according to different emission colors (Y-yellow, B-blue, BS-blue sky, P-purple, R-red, O-orange, W-white).

Figure 3. Differences in (a) superficial temperature (ΔT_{surf}) and (c) net SW radiation ($\Delta R_{SW,net}$) of the cool roof in its photoluminescent configuration and its non-luminescent version, according to different emission colors (Y-yellow, B-blue, BS-blue sky, P-purple, R-red, O-orange, W-white).

Figure 4. Comparison between superficial temperature (T_{surf}) and net SW radiation ($R_{SW,net}$) of the non-luminescent (non-lum) and red-emitting (R) roof. Monthly-averaged data for: (a) the hottest and (b) the coldest period of the year.

Figure 5 shows how, by maximizing the material’s ability to absorb solar radiation and emit light ($R_{opt}(Q_{Y,a})$), a more than doubled net shortwave radiation ($\approx 77 \text{ W/m}^2$) and surface temperature ($\approx 2.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) reduction could be obtained with respect to the non-luminescent case, if compared to the impact of a

real R-emitting material. Such significant results could be further improved if a more persistent photoluminescent materials can be developed for urban applications. Indeed, when modelling a red-emitting material with a more persistent photoluminescence ($R_{opt}(\tau \times 10^4)$), the impact of the phenomenon itself becomes more evident. The net shortwave radiation of $R_{opt}(\tau \times 10^4)$ and $R_{opt}(QY,a, \tau \times 10^4)$ profiles of figure 5c demonstrate how negative values of $R_{SW,net}$ occurred during the night period, indicating that the radiation emitted from the surface, i.e., the photoluminescence, was greater than the incident radiation. A 3-hour emission corresponded to a lifetime constant of the material equal to $\tau \times 10^4$, which is in line with data from literature on similar R-emitting materials. A longer photoluminescence decay also resulted in a slightly smoother and right-shifted $\Delta R_{SW,net}$ and ΔT_{surf} profiles, meaning that the peak in both net shortwave radiation and surface temperature of the roof were delayed during the day.

4. Conclusions

This study developed a numerical model to simulate the performance of a photoluminescent coating for roofs in mitigating the urban heat island effect. The model compared different photoluminescent compounds with various afterglow colors on both dark and cool roofs. The cooling effect of the compounds, in terms of temperature reduction and shortwave radiation reduction, was measured to identify the best-performing compound. The latter was deeper investigated during the hottest and coldest periods of the year, comparing the impact of photoluminescence on the roof's energy balance to the non-luminescent counterpart. The study found that the photoluminescent coating effectively reduced surface temperature and shortwave radiation when applied to a cool roof, with red-emitting coating showing the highest reduction in both temperature (≈ -1.2 °C) and net shortwave radiation (≈ -35 W/m²). The effects were more pronounced during the hottest period, while negligible effects were observed during winter. Additionally, the study suggests that by optimizing the photoluminescent material's properties, such as increasing absorption and emission capabilities, even greater reductions in surface temperature (≈ -2.4 °C) and shortwave radiation (≈ -77 W/m²) can be achieved. The findings highlight the potential of using photoluminescent materials to mitigate the urban heat island effect.

Figure 5. Comparison between differences in (a) superficial temperature (ΔT_{surf}) and (b) net SW radiation ($\Delta R_{SW,net}$) of the cool roof in its red-emitting configuration and its non-luminescent counterpart. The R coating has been considered in its real (R) and optimized (R_{opt}) status.

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